

AN AVIONICS INTEGRITY MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In silicon power transistor applications, thermal cycling of the transistor may activate a failure mechanism called thermal fatigue. This phenomenon is caused by the mechanical stresses set up by the differential in the thermal expansions of the various materials used in the assembly of the transistor and heat sink. Thermal fatigue often results in cracking of the silicon pellet or failure of the silicon mounting interface.

This paper provides a brief synopsis of the Avionics Integrity process along with an example of a mechanical analysis using the Avionics Integrity approach. The example involves the determination of the stress-strain relationships found in power transistors and an experimental approach for determining cycles to failure.

AVIONICS INTEGRITY PROGRAM

The Avionics Integrity Program represents a departure from the traditional approach to Reliability and Maintainability used in avionics design. The primary thrust of AVIP is that it requires a disciplined deterministic vice statistical approach for the Air Force Reliability and Maintainability Program. It requires the designer to understand the operational usage, material characteristics, life cycle environments and performance during the entire service life of the equipment. It also requires the establishment of design criteria that will ensure the system service life, while operating within these life cycle environments, will be achieved. The Avionics Integrity Program requires a complete understanding of the factors that cause electronics assemblies to fail. Electronic failures are mostly linked to a mechanical or material failure in some part or element of the electronic assembly. Failure trends which appear random over time, can be explained by well understood phenomena such as low-cycle fatigue induced by thermal cycling or high-cycle fatigue induced by vibration. Sometimes these failures are due to total times at power or elevated temperatures and calendar aging. Some examples of these latter types of failures are electromigration and oxide film formation.

Designers are now required to design the electronic equipment to function during a failure-free operating period. These requirements will

force the design towards the early part of the failure distribution curve rather than the mean and will thus greatly reduce the so called "random failures." An engineering analysis for the system is required prior to design release and is followed by testing that will identify residual failure modes. The durability of the design will be verified as part of the equipment qualification, a prerequisite to a production go-ahead decision.

The Avionics Integrity approach also requires that the designer be responsible for producibility. A well designed production process will result in the economic manufacture and consistently good quality of components. Avionics Integrity requires that the process be strictly controlled to the tolerances established in the design process or that the achievable manufacturing tolerances are recognized and accommodated in the design.

The Avionics Integrity approach questions the traditional presumption that avionics are allowed to fail in use and that only corrective maintenance is applicable. The requirements established by the user commands are simply not achievable using the traditional approach.

As the Avionics Integrity policies are implemented the life cycle management responsibilities will be reduced significantly. The contractors producing the design will be more closely involved in the equipment during the service life and there will be a dramatic increase in the environmental and failure data provided from fielded systems. In the long run, these efforts will save the government and the contractors significant amounts of money. The Avionics Integrity approach will be the mainstay of avionics system design for many years to come.

Figure 1 shows a portion of the Avionics Integrity Process schematic. The Mechanical Analysis of the avionics system is an integral part of the initial design development. After the determination of the design usage, installed environments and material characteristics of the required components; the design criteria can be developed.

The materials used in the electronic design shall have the properties necessary to meet the operational requirements for the service life and design usage of the electronics. The characteristics of each material used in the components should be specified in terms of the following:

1. strength; 2. stress or strain; 3. creep;
4. temperature-induced (low cycle) fatigue;
5. vibration-induced (high cycle) fatigue;
6. fracture toughness; 7. crack growth rate;
8. stress corrosion cracking; 9. corrosion resistance;
10. susceptibility to electromigration and operating temperature limits;
11. resistance to humidity; 12. resistance to chemicals;
13. resistance to biological materials;
14. resistance to radiological materials;
15. magnetic properties; 16. other characteristics/properties pertinent to the application

This data can then be used for the durability analysis which should be completed prior to drawing release. The data may be available within the literature or, if it is not, should be developed as part of the contracted effort. The material characterization should be contained in the AVIP Master Plan. A review of existing data on proposed materials and processes should be conducted along with a test plan to generate necessary additional data. The test plan should contain a materials listing for the electronics and identification of properties that should be characterized for each material. Methods of controlling the variability of the material characteristics should also be included. The plan should also include the tests that will assure that minimum properties will be attained.

Design criteria should be developed and applied in order to assure the equipment fulfills its integrity and performance requirements when operated within the installed and logistic environment. Based upon the material characteristics obtained for the avionic components, design criteria should be developed which will allow each of the components to function without failure for the service life of the equipment. These design criteria will limit the stress levels the components will experience in operational usage. The design criteria are actually derating criteria which are used to control the failure processes that are functions of time within the operational environment.

These derating factors are needed in the early stages of development because of the uncertainties in the design usage, environmental conditions and the quality of the finished product. The user will establish design life margins for the equipment and the contractor will then establish design margins for each part, item or material contained in the electronics, based upon their knowledge of the material characteristics and failure modes. The following engineering design parameters should be considered when the equipment design criteria is being determined.

1. Dielectric materials margin - There are three parameters that this design criteria should establish. The first is an operating voltage level. The operating voltage level should be determined by conducting a circuit analysis to determine nominal and worst-case voltage stresses. These stresses can be accommodated in the design by the conservative selection of material dimensions and process controls.

The second parameter that should be established is residual dielectric strength. Electrical systems can experience large transients and the dielectric should have sufficient strength at the completion of its lifetime to survive these transients without failure.

Finally, the design criteria should establish a maximum allowable mechanical strain in the insulation material such that no cracking of the dielectric materials occurs.

Dielectric material margins should be verified to ensure the dielectric materials will endure the required lifetime at the established operating voltage level. The worst-case voltage stress should be identified to determine the dielectric material's ability to withstand worst-case voltage conditions.

2. Current-carrying capacity - Electrical current-carrying materials used in the manufacture of electrical equipment shall have a specified service life, which is effected by electromigration and electrically accelerated corrosion. The current-carrying capacity should be verified by:

a. An analysis to determine the maximum current which will be carried by a given conductor, the cross section and conductance of the conductor, electromigration characteristics of the materials and inspection of the product.

b. Fatigue characteristics of the conductor should be verified by a demonstration of the equipment economic life.

c. Historical data

3. Design stress levels - This design criteria shall be established for each part and material such that no failure will occur in the service life when the equipment is exposed to the specified environments and mission profiles. These derating criteria should not be exceeded as they preclude unanticipated failure of the equipment. Compliance with this requirement should be demonstrated by analysis, inspection, thermal surveys and stress surveys.

4. Sensitivity of parts, assemblies and equipment to Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) - Protective devices should be incorporated within their design and process controls to preclude failure due to electrostatic discharge. Procedures should be established and implemented to control the adverse effects of ESD in the manufacturing and repair process.

5. Vibration - The electronic equipment shall be free of destructive resonances throughout the specified operating environment including potential flow resonances due to forced-air or liquid cooling. This shall include the coupling of vibration from the structure into the lower assemblies. A maximum printed wiring assembly deflection should be established to limit the adverse effects of vibration-induced fatigue.

A dynamic analysis should be conducted to establish component vibrational mode shapes and frequencies. An instrumented test should be accomplished to validate the results of the analysis.

6. Modification/rework of printed wiring assemblies - Modification or rework of printed wiring assemblies by the use of cuts and jumpers degrades the life characteristics of the printed wiring assemblies. The maximum allowable cuts and jumpers will be based on the contractor's experience. If the proposed criterion is less constraining than that contained in MIL-P-28809 then additional justification should be provided.

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

During thermal fatigue, a material or materials system is damaged as a result of repeated cyclic heating and cooling. Because this damage is often cumulative, failure of the systems may occur even if the tensile strength of the material is never approached. In many metals, mechanical fatigue failure is defined by a curve such as that shown in figure 2. If the stress never exceeds the value at the asymptotic part of the curve, the system life should not be limited by fatigue failure. Unfortunately, this minimum stress value can rarely be predicted without experimental data.

Materials that exhibit plastic deformation, such as lead (Pb), tend to recover partially or anneal at some critical temperature, and then show a change back to approximately their original condition. In the case of lead, thermal stress cycling can cause this annealing at temperatures even lower than the critical temperature.

In silicon power transistor applications, thermal cycling of the transistor may activate a failure mechanism called thermal fatigue. This phenomenon is caused by the mechanical stresses set up by the differential in the thermal expansions of the various materials used in the assembly and heat sink of the transistor. Thermal fatigue often results in cracking of the silicon pellet or failure at the silicon mounting interface. Two types of interfaces are encountered in power-transistor mounting systems. In type 1, the stress-strain relationship is treated in the elastic region. In type 2, at least one component exhibits material flow; therefore the stress-strain relationship is plastic. The following theoretical example will be confined to a type 1 system.

Figure 3 shows a simple bimetallic square of width L and length L that is joined rigidly at the interface. When this square is subjected to a change in temperature (ΔT), from T_1 to T_2 , stress forces develop.

In the elastic region for the two materials A and B the strain relationship may be expressed as follows:

$$(a_A - a_B)(\Delta T) = (1/2r)(t_A + t_B) + F_A(1-p_A) / (E_A t_A L + F_B(1-p_B) / E_B t_B L)$$

where a is a linear coefficient of thermal expansion for each material, r is the radius of curvature of the square, t is the thickness of the material, E is Young's modulus, L is the length of the interface and p is Poisson's ratio.

Application of a force F in one direction stretches the solid by a strain eL in the direction of the applied force, and by an amount $-peL$ in a direction transverse to F ($e = \Delta L/L$), as shown in figure 4. If an identical and opposite force F is applied normal to faces 1 and 2, the elastic distortion of the solid results in a square of sides $L(1+e-pe)$ which can be written as $L(1+e(1-p))$.

If E represents Young's modulus for the solid then $e = F/LtE$, and the elastic strain component is $(F/LtE)(1-p)$.

For a composite solid which is formed by joining a pair of materials together the thermal strain caused by a temperature cycle, ΔT is $(\Delta T)(a_A - a_B)$ where $(a_A - a_B)$ is the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion. As the composite solid bends to relieve the elastic stress, a bending strain $(1/r)((t_A + t_B)/2)$ results, where r is the radius of curvature in the composite structure. Equating the thermal strain to the sum of the bending and elastic strains provides the given relationship.

In the design of a mounting system for a silicon power transistor, all of the factors in the equation are known except r , F_A and F_B . If the joining interface is neglected the following additional equations can be defined.

$$\text{Force Equation: } F_A - F_B = 0$$

$$\text{Moment Equation: } (1/12r)(E_A t_A^3 + E_B t_B^3) = (F_B/L)(t_B/2) + F_A/L(t_A/2)$$

In a typical silicon transistor design problem, it is often necessary to consider the shear forces at several interfaces, as well as their interactions. A typical power transistor may have the configuration shown in figure 5. The joining materials are very thin and have no appreciable effect on the force configuration of the system.

Figure 5A compares the system of forces for a package of the Si-Mo-Cu-Steel configuration with that for a package which used no Molybdenum. The solutions are obtained for a .26 by .26 inch silicon pellet for a temperature change of 65°C. The effect of the molybdenum is to reduce the shearing force at the silicon-package interface. The optimum design of a package involves the selection of a set of materials that will present the least stress at the Si-package interface and achieve minimum transient and steady-state thermal resistance. Minimum stress at the silicon-package interface alleviates the problem of cracking of the silicon pellet or failure of the silicon mounting interface in thermal fatigue.

The next topic of discussion will be the analysis of soft-solder or type I systems. Recall that

these systems exhibit material "flow" in at least one of the components and therefore the stress-strain relationship is plastic. Figure 6 shows thermal fatigue data for transistors in which a high lead content solder is used to mount the silicon pellet to a nickel plated copper heat sink. In this figure n represents the number of cycles to failure, where a cycle consists of two minutes of heating and three minutes of cooling, and a failure is defined as a change in thermal resistance of 25 percent or more. L is the maximum pellet dimension. The solid-line, curve A, shows experimental data for a delta T or 47°C. The bottom curve B shows the effect of a change in delta T from 47 to 65°C. This curve, which indicates a shorter time to failure for a larger temperature change, has been shown correct by experimental data and quantitative analysis.

The thermal fatigue capability of a power transistor is usually stated as a minimum number of cycles at a given temperature variation before failure. This type of rating must be extrapolated to the particular conditions under which a transistor will be operated. Accelerated thermal fatigue tests are necessary to provide data within a reasonable length of time. Because thermal time constants of the transistor represent a practical limit to the rate at which temperature can be cycled, for rapid results the stress must be increased. Figure 7 shows the results of an accelerated test in which the temperature variation, delta T, was increased from 55 to 110°C. Thermal-fatigue damage to silicon power transistors is usually caused by increased thermal resistance of a portion of the chip to the header on which it is mounted. Traditionally, transistors have been thermally cycled until the damage to the electrical characteristics become obvious. A thermal-resistance test can detect damage long before electrical degradation occurs.

Figure 8 shows a simple circuit which can be used to determine experimentally the number of cycles before failure occurs in a power transistor. The circuit can be modified as necessary to avoid parasitic oscillation. The modification is determined by the frequency response of the transistor tested and generally takes the form of capacitors, usually connected collector-to-emitter. A thermal-fatigue test is basically a cyclical, operating life test. The important test parameters for room ambient testing are: change in junction temperature, maximum junction temperature, junction to case thermal resistance and cycle time. The most important parameter in the empirical determination of the power-cycling capability of power transistors has been the change in junction temperature. Although the maximum junction temperature and cycle time are also factors, the most useful predictive method is based on the change in junction temperature. This can be compared to the traditional reliability prediction techniques, where junction temperature is used to obtain a failure rate. When maximum junction temperature is specified, the unintended result is the specification of, a predetermined minimum time

to failure with a specified design usage or duty cycle for the failure mechanisms that have been discussed.

This circuit and the accelerated thermal cycle test described earlier could easily be utilized as an environmental stress screen for the transistor and also to establish the characteristics of each manufacturing lot by an easily accomplished sample test. Such a test might involve the testing of a small sample (possibly 10 units) with no failures occurring before X cycles and no more than some small number of failures (possibly two) occurring before Y cycles. This would give the user an indication of the life characteristics of the manufacturing lot for a rather small investment.

In summary, It has been shown that the Avionics Integrity approach is a viable technique for designing reliable electronic systems. The Avionics Integrity process does not necessarily require the development of new engineering techniques but simply provides the guidelines for applying those engineering analysis techniques which are currently being used in industry. Today, I have just touched the tip of the iceberg regarding the Avionics Integrity Process. When all aspects of the Avionics Integrity Process are considered in total the final product will be much more reliable.

REFERENCES

1. G. A. Lang, B. J. Fehder, W. D. Williams, "Thermal Fatigue in Silicon Power Transistors", IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, September 1970
2. L. J. Gallace, W. R. Peterson, "Reliability and Control of Semiconductor Parameters for Switching Regulators", RCA Application Note, ST-6399

THE AVIP PROCESS

FIGURE 1

BIMETALLIC SQUARE

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 2

TYPICAL POWER TRANSISTOR MOUNT ASSEMBLIES

FIGURE 5

STRAINS IN A SOLID UNDER MECHANICAL STRESS

FIGURE 4

RESULTS

<u>MATERIAL</u>	<u>THERMAL COEFFICIENT OF EXPANSION PER C</u>	<u>THICKNESS (INCH)</u>	<u>YOUNG'S MODULUS (PSI)</u>	<u>FORCE WITHOUT MO (LBS)</u>	<u>FORCE WITH MO (LBS)</u>
SILICON	3×10^{-6}	7.89×10^{-3}	26×10^5	-32	-11
MOLYBDENUM	6×10^{-6}	2.99×10^{-2}	51.4×10^6		-39.3
COPPER	17.5×10^{-6}	9.37×10^{-2}	18×10^6	55	89
STEEL	14×10^{-6}	6.3×10^{-2}	30×10^6	-23	-28.9
<u>INTERFACE</u>	<u>MOLYBDENUM (LBS)</u>	<u>SHEARING STRESS (LBS/IN²)</u>	<u>NO MOLYBDENUM SHEARING FORCE (LBS)</u>	<u>SHEARING STRESS (LBS/IN²)</u>	
FCU - FSTEEL	117	1740	78	1150	
FCU - FMO	128	1980			
FSI - FMO	28	420			
FSI - FCU				1300	

87 FIGURE 5A

EXAMPLE TEST CIRCUIT

